

Inhibition of Corrosion of B26S Aluminium in Phosphoric Acid by some Azo Dyes[†]

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At constant acid concentration the inhibitive efficiency of various azo dyes for Al-4% Cu alloy in phosphoric acid increases with inhibitor concentration but at constant inhibitor concentration the efficiency decreases with increase in acid concentration and temperature. A 0.2% inhibitor in 0.033 M acid conferred 19.0 (methyl red) to 54.9% (naphthol blue black) protection. Of the various azo dyes those containing a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen show better efficiency. Metanil yellow, fast sulphon black F and fast garnet are comparatively better inhibitors in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid. In phosphoric nitric and sulphuric acids naphthol blue black is a good inhibitor, whereas in oxalic acid eriochrome black T shows an efficiency of 30%. In mixed hydrochloric-phosphoric acids naphthol blue black gives ~26% inhibition.

The corrosion potential of -755 mV (vs SCE) for B26S aluminium in 0.033 M phosphoric acid is not much affected by the inhibitor. Under galvanostatic polarisation conditions, the anode is polarised to a greater extent than the cathode. The dyes appear to function through adsorption following Langmuir isotherm.

SOLUTIONS of phosphoric acid are frequently employed for cleaning aluminium, in commercial preplating anodic oxidation and in chemical polishing or etching of aluminium¹. For electroplating phosphoric acid baths containing thiourea, ethylene glycol, glucose, gelatin, etc., are used² as additives. Although dyes are used to give multi-coloured effects to anodised aluminium surfaces, data regarding their effect on the acid corrosion of aluminium is not much available^{3,4}. In continuation of our earlier work⁵, the present work deals with the effects of some azo dyes on the corrosion of B26S aluminium (Al-4% Cu) in phosphoric acid.

Experimental

The composition of the alloy, the specimen size and the method of carrying out the corrosion tests were the same as described earlier⁵. The test specimens were exposed to phosphoric acid solutions in the concentration range 0.033–0.66 M containing 0.01–0.2% of azo dyes. For galvanostatic polarisation studies circular metal coupons (dia. 28.4 mm with a handle 32.2 × 4.8 mm) were used. The area exposed to the test solution was 6.33 cm² while the polarising current density was varied in the range 1.58 × 10⁻⁶ to 7.90 × 10⁻⁴ A cm⁻². The potentials were recorded with an accuracy of ±5 mV by a Philips D.C. microvoltmeter.

The specimens immersed in dilute solutions of phosphoric acid were covered with a greyish, loose, thin film which could be easily removed by rubbing

with a rubber bung. In concentrated acid, the film was thicker and dark grey in appearance. The inhibited acid specimens were covered with a loose film of the same colour as the dye and it could be easily removed by the cleaning solution. The surface of the corroded specimens, on cleaning, showed a dull metallic appearance.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Tables 1–4 and Figs. 1–6. Azo dyes like metanil yellow, alizarin yellow, naphthol blue black, fast sulphon black F, methyl red, eriochrome black T, resorcin yellow and fast garnet were added to 0.033–0.667 M phosphoric acid containing 0.01–0.2% of the dye. The pH values of 0.1% aqueous solutions of the inhibitors were in the range 3.25 (fast garnet) to 9.20 (fast sulphon black F), inhibitors being noncorrosive to aluminium. The pH of 0.33 M phosphoric acid was found to be 1.80 while the values for inhibited acid (0.033 M H₃PO₄ + 0.1% inhibitor) were observed in the range 1.80–1.85, i.e. the inhibitors had little effect on the pH of the acid.

Effect of inhibitor concentration: In order to determine the effect of inhibitor concentration on inhibitive efficiency, weight losses were determined in 0.033 M phosphoric acid containing 0.01–0.2% of the inhibitor. The results (Fig. 1) show that the inhibitive efficiency of all the inhibitors increases with increasing inhibitor concentration. At 0.2% inhibitor concentration, the efficiency was found to

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Fig. 1. Effect of inhibitor concentration of inhibitive efficiency of azo dyes for B26S aluminium in 0.033 M phosphoric acid (30°, 1 day).

Fig. 2. Effect of concentration of phosphoric acid on inhibitive efficiency of azo dyes for B26S aluminium (30°, 1 day).

increase in the order : methyl red (19.0%) < fast garnet (24.0%) < metanil yellow (37.4%) < eriochrome black T (38.8%) < alizarin yellow (39.2%) < resorcine yellow (45.9%) < fast sulphon black F (50.4%) < naphthol blue black (54.0%).

Effect of acid concentration : In order to determine the effect of acid concentration on inhibitive

efficiency, weight losses were measured in 0.033–0.667 M phosphoric acid containing a constant inhibitor concentration of 0.1%. The results (Table 2) show that B26S aluminium undergoes a weight loss of 33.7 mg in 0.033 M plain phosphoric acid at 30° in one day. As the concentration of the acid is increased, the loss in weight increases and is found to be 208.2 mg in plain 0.667 M acid. In inhibited acid the weight losses are slightly lower. The results also show that there is a decrease in efficiency with increase in acid concentration (Fig. 2), it being more so with inhibitors like naphthol blue black, which incidentally happen to be good inhibitors in 0.033 M phosphoric acid. The order of increase in efficiency of the inhibitors in 0.033 M acid is found to be : methyl red (4.5%) < fast garnet (17.2%) < metanil yellow (20.8%) < eriochrome black T (24.5%) < alizarin yellow (26.1%) < fast sulphon black F (33.5%) < resorcine yellow (38.3%) < naphthol blue black (45.1%). In 0.667 M phosphoric acid, the efficiency is found to increase in the order : methyl red (0.8%) < metanil yellow (2.0%) < fast garnet (3.8%) < eriochrome black T (5.1%) < alizarin yellow (6.6%) < fast sulphon black F (6.8%) < naphthol blue black (11.5%) < resorcine yellow (18.3%).

Effect of temperature : In order to study the effect of temperature on inhibitive efficiency, weight losses were determined in 0.167 M phosphoric acid containing 0.1% of inhibitor at solution temperatures of 30, 40, 50 and 60° for an exposure period of 5 h. The results (Table 1 and Fig. 3) reveal that the loss in weight due to corrosion in plain acid increases with temperature, it being almost doubled for every 10° rise in temperature.

In 0.167 M phosphoric acid containing 0.1% inhibitor, it was found that there is an increase in weight loss and a decrease in efficiency with a rise in temperature, there being a two fold increase in corrosion for every 10° rise in temperature. In general, the order of increase in efficiency of the inhibitors is found to be : methyl red < metanil yellow < alizarin yellow < fast garnet < eriochrome black T < resorcine yellow < fast sulphon black F < naphthol blue black.

The values of the energy of activation were calculated with the help of Arrhenius equation and also

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON CORROSION OF B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.167 M PHOSPHORIC ACID CONTAINING AZO DYES

Specimen size = 5 × 4 cm, Inhibitor concentration = 0.1% ; Exposure period = 5 h.

Inhibitor	Weight loss (mg) at				E kJ mol ⁻¹	Q kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG ⁰ kJ mol ⁻¹
	30°	40°	50°	60°			
Nil	23.4	44.7	85.4	152.2	51.5	—	—
Metanil yellow	19.7	38.1	76.2	145.5	55.2	-79.1	-10.9
Alizarin yellow	19.2	37.5	75.1	144.5	56.5	-75.7	-11.3
Naphthol blue black	15.2	31.0	62.8	118.2	56.1	-17.6	-14.2
Fast sulphon black F	15.8	32.5	66.3	126.0	56.5	-27.2	-13.6
Methyl red	20.2	40.2	80.1	148.2	56.5	-65.3	-10.9
Eriochrome black T	17.3	35.2	70.5	134.7	52.3	-49.4	-12.8
Resorcine yellow	14.1	31.2	68.4	136.8	62.7	-41.4	-13.4
Fast garnet	18.2	38.5	76.4	145.0	56.5	-38.4	-11.3

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on inhibitive efficiency of some azo dyes for B26S aluminium in 0.167 M phosphoric acid.

from the slopes of plots of $\log \sigma$ vs $1/T$. The values (Table 1) show that the energy of activation for the corrosion process in plain 0.167 M phosphoric acid is $\sim 52 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. In inhibited acid, the E values are almost the same as that in the uninhibited acid. However, resorcine yellow gives a slightly higher value of 62.7 kJ mol^{-1} , suggesting that the decrease in efficiency with a rise in temperature is more with resorcine yellow. The almost similar values of E in uninhibited and inhibited acid suggest that the nature of the corrosion process is almost the same in plain as well as in inhibited acid⁶. The almost similar values of E in all the cases in inhibited acid further show that the mechanism of inhibitive action is the same for all the inhibitors.

The values of heat of adsorption (Q) of different inhibitors were calculated with the help of equation (1),

$$Q = 2.303 \times R \left[\log \frac{\theta_2}{1-\theta_2} - \log \frac{\theta_1}{1-\theta_1} \right] \left[\frac{T_1 \times T_2}{T_2 - T_1} \right] \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Plots of $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ vs $1/T$ for corrosion of B26S aluminium in 0.167 M phosphoric acid containing 0.1% inhibitor.

The Q values were also calculated (Table 1) from the plots of $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 4). The results show that the heat of adsorption is minimum ($-17.6 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) in the case of naphthol blue black and maximum ($-79.1 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$) in case of metanil yellow.

The values of free energy of adsorption (ΔG_A°) were calculated using equation :

$$\log C = \log \frac{\theta}{1-\theta} - \log B \quad (2)$$

where, $\log B = -1.74 - (\Delta G_A^\circ / 2.303 RT)$ (3)

The values (Table 1) show that the free energy of adsorption varies from -10.9 (metanil yellow and methyl red) to $-14.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ (naphthol blue black), i.e. ΔG_A° values do not differ much. However, naphthol blue black and fast sulphon black F, which show slightly higher efficiency than metanil yellow or methyl red, have slightly more negative free energies of adsorption.

Polarisation behaviour : A specimen of B26S aluminium when immersed in uninhibited 0.033 M phosphoric acid, develops a corrosion potential of -755 mv (vs SCE) (Table 2). In the presence of

TABLE 2—TABLE PARAMETERS AND INHIBITORS EFFICIENCIES OF AZO DYES FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.033 M PHOSPHORIC ACID

Surface area of specimen = 6.33 cm^2 , Inhibitor concentration = 0.002 M , Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$

Inhibitor	E_{corr} mV vs SCE	β_c V/decade	β_a V/decade	α_c	I_{corr} (A cm^{-2}) from		Inhibitor efficiency (%) calculated from		
					Cathodic Tafel plot $\times 10^{-5}$	Anodic Tafel plot $\times 10^{-5}$	Cathodic Tafel plot	Anodic Tafel plot	Weight loss
Nil	-755	0.08	0.12	0.80	4.17	4.17	—	—	—
Metanil yellow	-740	0.08	0.13	0.74	3.55	3.55	14.9	14.9	16.2
Alizarin yellow	-750	0.07	0.12	0.86	3.39	3.89	18.9	18.7	18.1
Naphthol blue black	-770	0.05	0.07	1.13	2.23	2.51	45.0	39.7	48.3
Fast sulphon black F	-750	0.09	0.14	0.03	2.40	2.51	42.5	39.7	41.9
Methyl red	-760	0.10	0.32	0.61	3.98	3.98	4.5	4.5	3.9
Eriochrome black T	-760	0.08	0.17	0.72	3.16	3.24	24.1	22.4	22.8
Resorcine yellow	-765	0.11	0.14	0.56	2.63	2.82	36.9	34.4	40.2
Fast garnet	-740	0.11	0.18	0.52	3.63	3.72	12.9	10.9	13.4

various inhibitors, the corrosion potentials are found to be almost the same (within ± 15 mV) as that in the uninhibited acid. Galvanostatic polarisation curves (Fig. 5) show the polarisation of both, the cathode as well as the anode, the anode being polarised to a greater extent.

Fig. 5. Effect of current density on cathode and anode potentials of B26S aluminium in 0.033 M phosphoric acid containing 0.002 M inhibitor.

The values of cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes, corrosion currents and the inhibitive efficiencies obtained therefrom are given in Table 2. It is evident that the cathodic as well as the anodic Tafel slopes in inhibited acid are almost the same as that in uninhibited acid. The similar values of the Tafel slopes and the same nature of Tafel plots suggest that the electrochemical behaviour is the same in inhibited and uninhibited acids. The inhibitive efficiencies calculated from anodic and cathodic Tafel plots almost agree with those obtained from weight loss data.

Comparative behaviour of azo dyes in different acids: As the azo dyes were found not to confer much protection on B26S aluminium in phosphoric acid, an attempt was also made to study the inhibitive effect of these dyes in 0.1 N solutions of acids, like hydrochloric, sulphuric, nitric and oxalic. The results (Table 3) show that in plain acids, at 0.1 N concentration, the extent of corrosion increases in the order: H_2SO_4 (14.4 mg) < HCl (16.4 mg) < $H_2C_2O_4$ (20.2 mg) < HNO_3 (21.5 mg) < H_3PO_4 (33.7

mg). In inhibited acids, the weight losses were slightly lower but none of the azo dyes was able to confer more than 50% protection to B26S aluminium.

As the different inhibitors show different efficiencies in various acids, it is very difficult to draw far reaching conclusions. However, it may be generalised that methyl red exhibits minimum efficiency in all the acids while naphthol blue black exhibits maximum efficiency in 0.1 N solutions of phosphoric, sulphuric and nitric acids. Metanil yellow gives more protection in hydrochloric acid while eriochrome black T in oxalic acid.

Corrosion in a mixture of hydrochloric and phosphoric acids: Earlier⁴, the inhibitive efficiency of azo dyes was shown to increase with the acid concentration in hydrochloric acid, whereas in phosphoric acid, the efficiency was found to decrease with increasing acid concentration. An attempt was, therefore, made to study the corrosion in a mixture of the two acids, each being present at 0.1 N concentration, i.e. the overall normality of the solution being 0.2 N. The results are given in Table 4. The results reveal that alizarin yellow, fast sulphon black F and eriochrome black T show lowest efficiency in the mixture. Metanil yellow almost fails to protect B26S aluminium in the acid mixture, whereas the efficiency of naphthol blue black in the mixture is slightly higher than that in hydrochloric acid, but quite lower than in phosphoric acid. Methyl red confers only 4.5% protection in 0.1 N phosphoric acid and accelerates the corrosion in hydrochloric acid by 14%. However, in the mixture, the acceleration was 6.6%. The results thus exhibit that the phosphate ion probably has a detrimental effect on the inhibitive efficiency of the inhibitors.

Mechanism of inhibition: Structurally the various dyes studied may be subclassified into the following groups: (i) dyes containing an azo group, two benzene rings and three substituent groups of which two are on the same ring, e.g. resorcinol yellow and alizarin yellow, (ii) dyes containing three nitrogens, of which two are azoic and one is aminic, and two benzene rings with some

TABLE 3—INHIBITIVE EFFICIENCY OF AZO DYES FOR B26S ALUMINIUM IN 0.1 N CONCENTRATION OF DIFFERENT ACIDS

Surface area of specimen = 40 cm², Temp. = 30 ± 0.5°, Immersion period = 1 day, Inhibitor concentration = 0.1%

Inhibitor	0.1 N HCl		0.1 N H ₂ SO ₄		0.1 N HNO ₃		0.1 N H ₂ C ₂ O ₄		0.1 N H ₃ PO ₄	
	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.
Nil	16.4	—	14.4	—	21.5	—	20.2	—	33.7	—
Metanil yellow	9.8	40.2	12.7	11.8	19.8	7.9	16.0	20.8	26.7	20.8
Alizarin yellow	13.5	17.7	12.6	12.5	16.5	23.2	19.7	2.5	24.9	26.1
Naphthol blue black	12.7	22.6	10.2	29.2	12.5	41.9	19.9	1.5	18.5	45.1
Fast sulphon black F	9.8	40.2	12.9	10.4	14.5	32.5	16.8	16.8	22.4	33.5
Methyl red	18.7	-14.0	13.4	6.9	19.5	9.3	20.1	0.5	32.2	4.5
Eriochrome black T	10.5	36.0	12.6	12.5	18.1	15.8	14.1	30.2	25.6	24.5
Fast garnet	9.8	40.2	—	—	—	—	—	—	20.8	38.3
Resorcinol yellow	10.2	37.8	—	—	—	—	—	—	27.9	17.2

substituent groups, e.g. fast garnet, (iii) dyes containing two naphthalene rings and three nitrogens, of which two are azoic and the third one belonging to NO_2 group, e.g. eriochrome black T, (iv) dyes containing two azo groups (four azoic nitrogens), three naphthalene rings, three SO_3Na groups and two OH groups, e.g. fast sulphon black F, and (v) dyes containing six nitrogens, four from two azo groups, one from NH_2 group and one from NO_2 group, one naphthalene ring, two SO_3Na groups and one OH group, e.g. naphthol blue black.

The order of increase in inhibitive efficiency of the four inhibitors which contain one azo group having a benzene ring, with one or two substituent groups, on each of the azoic nitrogens, is found to be as follows: methyl red < fast garnet < alizarin yellow < resorcline yellow. Resorcline yellow contains two OH groups, one is *ortho*- and the other in *meta*-position to the azoic nitrogen. According to Venkataraman⁶, the compounds containing a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azo group can form complexes with metals through the oxygen of the hydroxy group and the nitrogen of the azo group. If the inhibitor is considered to be adsorbed through the functional azo group, then the better efficiency of resorcline yellow may be attributed to this complex formation because of the *o*-hydroxy group.

In alizarin yellow, the *o*-hydroxy group is absent and therefore, unlike resorcline yellow, the advantage of complex formation is not available here. In addition, there is a COOH group with $-\text{R}$, $-\text{I}$, effects which may decrease the electron density on the azoic nitrogen and thus alizarin yellow will show efficiencies lower than resorcline yellow.

In fast garnet, a NH_2 group is present in *para*-position to one of the azoic nitrogens. It also contains a CH_2 group in *ortho*-position to the NH_2 group and *meta*-position to the same azoic nitrogen. In addition, there is also a CH_3 group in *ortho*-position to the other azoic nitrogen. Fast garnet shows inhibitive efficiency lower than alizarin yellow and resorcline yellow.

In methyl red, the two aminic hydrogens are replaced by two electron-releasing CH_3 groups, while electron density on one of the azoic nitrogens

is decreased by the presence of COO^- group in *ortho*-position to this nitrogen. As a result, the adsorptive power of the dye via the functional azo group appears to have been lost and thus methyl red shows the minimum efficiency of all the eight compounds studied.

Metanil yellow has a structure somewhat similar to fast garnet, one of the hydrogens of the NH_2 group being replaced by the C_6H_5 group, while the two CH_3 groups are absent, but in addition one SO_3Na group is present and therefore, in general, the efficiencies of metanil yellow and fast garnet are almost equal within the limits of experimental error.

In eriochrome black T, a naphthalene ring is attached to each of the azoic nitrogens with a OH group in *ortho*-position to azoic nitrogen on one of the rings. Thus the inhibitive effect of eriochrome black T is greater than methyl red, fast garnet and metanil yellow but lower than resorcline yellow, probably because of the steric hindrance due to presence of naphthalene rings.

Fast sulphon black F contains two azo groups, three naphthalene rings and two OH groups, each in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen. The efficiency of fast sulphon black F should, therefore, be better than

Fig. 6. Plots of $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ vs \log inhibitor concentration.

TABLE 4—COMPARATIVE BEHAVIOUR OF VARIOUS INHIBITORS IN HYDROCHLORIC AND PHOSPHORIC ACIDS AND THEIR MIXTURE

Surface area of specimen = 40 cm^2 , Inhibitor concentration = 0.1%, Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, Immersion period = 1 day

Inhibitors	0.1 N HCl + 0.1 N H_2PO_4		0.2 N HCl		0.2 N H_2PO_4	
	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.	Loss mg	P.I.
Nil	46.7	—	30.2	—	49.2	—
Metanil yellow	48.2	-3.2	14.3	52.6	43.8	10.9
Alizarin yellow	39.6	15.2	20.4	32.5	39.2	20.3
Naphthol blue black	34.5	26.1	19.1	36.8	28.5	42.1
Fast sulphon black F	42.3	9.4	14.6	51.6	35.2	28.5
Methyl red	49.8	-6.6	—	—	48.0	2.4
Eriochrome black T	45.4	2.8	—	—	40.0	18.7
Resorcline yellow	—	—	14.9	49.3	31.7	35.6
Fast garnet	—	—	14.6	51.6	41.8	15.0

the dyes containing one azo group with a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen. But because of the presence of three SO₃Na groups and the steric hindrance effects due to the naphthalene rings, it shows efficiencies greater than inhibitors like methyl red, fast garnet, metanil yellow, eriochrome black T and alizarin yellow, but lower than resorcline yellow and naphthol blue black.

Naphthol blue black also contains two azo groups, two SO₃Na groups in *ortho*-position to the two azoic nitrogens, a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen and a NH₂ group also in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen. Further, as the two naphthalene rings of fast sulphon black F have been replaced by benzene rings, the steric hindrance appears to have been somewhat reduced and therefore naphthol blue black shows better efficiencies than other inhibitors.

In general, it may be concluded that the dyes containing a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azoic nitrogen show better efficiency, e.g. naphthol blue black, resorcline yellow and fast sulphon black F. Eriochrome black T also contains a OH group in *ortho*-position to the azo group but because of the presence of groups like NO₂ and SO₃Na, its capability to be chemisorbed appears to have been slightly decreased. Thus eriochrome black T and alizarin yellow which contain a OH group in *para*-position to the azo group exhibit almost the same inhibitive effect, being lower than naphthol blue black, resorcline yellow and fast sulphon black F. Inhibitors like methyl red, metanil yellow and fast garnet contain an NR₂ group (R=H, -CH₃ and / or -C₆H₅) in *para*-position to the azoic nitrogen and, therefore, show efficiencies lower than the other five compounds. The lowest efficiency of methyl red may also be due to the presence of a positive charge on the azoic nitrogen which might reduce its adsorptivity.

The corrosion potentials of B26S aluminium in inhibited 0.033 *M* phosphoric acid are found to be almost the same (within ±15 mV) as that in plain

phosphoric acid. This suggests that the inhibitors do not have any preferential effect on the local anodes or cathodes. The values of the cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes also confirm this. Thus the inhibitors appear to function through adsorption on both cathodic as well as anodic areas in a more general manner. The linearity of the plots of log $\theta/(1-\theta)$ vs log inhibitor concentration (Fig. 6) also suggests that the inhibitors function through adsorption following Langmuir isotherm.

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